

In 1985-88 trials, grain yields were generally slightly higher at Befang. Plants were shorter and growth duration much longer at Babungo (see table), reflecting the cooler temperatures that adversely affected crop growth there. The highest yielding entries were ITA208 and IRAT109 at Befang and IRAT112 and IRAT109 at Babungo. Across sites, the highest yields were from IRAT109, ITA208, and IRAT112.

IRAT 109, a derivative of IRAT 13/IRAT10, has medium-long grain with white bran. IRAT112 from IRAT13/Dourado Precoce is similar to IRAT109 in agronomic trait, but has slender grain, which is more acceptable to consumers. ITA208, a derivative of 63-83/(Vijaya, Dourado Precoce, Jumai) has medium-long, bold grain with white bran. ROK16, a selection from the traditional varieties of Sierra Leone, has broad leaves, awned spikelets, and medium and bold grains.

M55 is an improved upland variety currently grown by a few farmers. It is a mutant of 63-83 and has medium and bold grains. ■

Surveys of disease or insect incidence/severity in one environment are useful only if the information is related to other variables (e.g., climatic factors, crop intensification, cultivars, management practices, etc.). By itself, information on incidence in one environment does not increase scientific knowledge.

Integrated germplasm improvement — deepwater

Three promising deepwater rice varieties for Sichuan

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About 200,000 ha of tanks, weirs, and lakes in Sichuan Province with water depths of 50-150 cm are the primary source of irrigation water for a large hectareage of irrigated ricelands. The introduction of deepwater rice cultivation could increase total production, and better meet the food needs of a rapidly growing population.

In 1988-89, we evaluated promising deepwater rice cultivars IR41336-6-2-1-1, B4406D-MR-2-7, and B5278-13D-

MR-6-3 selected from the International Rice Deep Water Observational Nursery (IRDWON). IR41336-6-2-1-1-1 was derived from RD19/Badal 116; B4406D-MR-2-7 from SML Tomerin/B2360-6-7-1//Tetep/B2474B-1-PN-2-3-2-2-5; and B5278-13D-MR-6-3 from Lagos/IR9129-457-2-2-1-2//FR13A/IR3351-38-3-1.

They appear to be adaptable to Sichuan circumstances and are being

recommended for demonstration trials in farmers' fields (see table). IR41336-6-2-1-1-1 has strong culms and dark green leaves, with medium slender, fine, white grain. B4406D-MR-2-7 and B5278-13D-MR-6-3 have medium bold grain. All three cultivars have very good submergence tolerance, kneeling ability, and plant type. They are moderately resistant to blast. ■

Agricultural characteristics of 3 promising deepwater rice cultivars in Luzhou, Sichuan, China (mean of 1988-1989).

Character	IR41336-6-2-1-1-1	B4406D-MR-2-7	B5278-13D-MR-6-3
Culm length (cm)	155.4	136.3	141.7
Growth duration (d)	175.0	184.0	174.0
Panicles/plant (no.)	6.8	6.2	5.5
Panicle length (cm)	30.6	26.8	32.4
Filled spikelets/panicle (no.)	178.3	138.6	161.2
1000-grain weight (g)	24.7	25.4	27.8
Grain yield (t/ha)	3.4	3.3	3.2

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Soils

Exchangeable Al as a criterion of lime requirement for rice in acid sulfate soil

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A field study was conducted to determine whether exchangeable Al can serve as basis for lime requirement to maximize the yield of rice in an acid sulfate soil.

Effects of lime levels on yield and nutrient uptake of rice grown in acid sulfate soil. Nirdeshkali, West Bengal.

Lime rate (t CaCO ₃ /ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Nutrient uptake (mg/kg)				
		N	P	K	Fe	Al
No lime	1.7	21.0	6.7	47.1	10.2	8.1
3.6	2.0	22.2	7.4	49.8	9.8	7.5
5.5	2.3	25.0	7.7	50.2	8.9	7.5
7.3	2.3	28.2	9.5	60.2	7.8	6.6
9.1	4.0	51.6	20.0	70.4	4.5	4.2
11.0	3.8	48.4	19.9	70.7	4.5	5.0
12.8	3.7	47.8	19.3	70.9	5.0	4.9
14.6	3.3	48.6	18.4	72.9	4.6	5.1
16.4	3.0	46.5	11.3	73.4	5.1	5.2
18.2	2.8	35.9	7.1	59.4	5.3	5.3
LSD (0.01)	6.7	6.7	3.5	5.7	1.4	2.1

The experimental site was a lowland ricefield with irrigation facilities in Nirdeshkhali in the coastal area of West Bengal. The soil belonged to mixed, hyperthermic acidic family of Typic Haplaquept. Important characteristics were pH (1:2 water) 3.3, 1.95% organic C, 63% clay (illite dominant), CEC 28.9 meq/100 g, 0.123% total N, 9.8 mg available P/kg, exchangeable K 2.12 meq/100 g, and exchangeable Al 0.911 meq/100 g. Lime required to raise soil pH to 5.5 was 33.21 t CaCO₃/ha.

The experiment was laid out in 20- m² plots, in a randomized block design with four replications. The field was plowed thoroughly, and required lime (CaCO₃) applied before the field was puddled. At harvest, grain yield was sampled and uptake of N, P, K, Fe, and Al determined.

Grain yield of rice MW10 was highest when lime corresponding to 10 times the amount of exchangeable Al (9.11 t CaCO₃/ha) was applied. That amount increased soil pH and counter-

acted the ill effects of Fe and Al. Nutrient uptake by grain was also highest at that lime level (see table). The results indicate that yield was maximized with lime equivalent to or less than the amounts theoretically needed to neutralize toxic quantities of Fe and Al and supply adequate Ca.

Exchangeable Al served as a good estimator of lime required for economic productivity of rice in this acid sulfate soil. ■

Soil microbiology

Response of *Azolla pinnata* to herbicide and time of inoculation

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We evaluated the response of azolla to rice herbicides—anilofos alone and in combination with 2,4-D EE (ethyl ester) and thiobencarb + 2,4-D EE—in terms of fresh biomass (FB), relative growth rate (RGR), and chlorophyll content 20 d after herbicide application. Azolla was inoculated 0, 3, and 6 d after herbicide application.

Untreated control recorded the highest FB (see table), but FB with anilofos alone and in combination with 2,4-D EE were comparable. FB was significantly reduced with thiobencarb + 2,4-D EE.

Effects of herbicides and time of azolla inoculation on fresh biomass, RGR, and chlorophyll content of *Azolla pinnata*.^a Coimbatore, India.

Treatment	Fresh biomass (t/ha)	RGR (g/g per d)	Chlorophyll (mg/g)	
			'a'	'b'
Herbicides				
Thiobencarb + 2,4-D EE (1.00 + 0.51 kg/ha)	11.22 c	0.20 b	2.30 a	1.39 a
Anilofos + 2,4-D EE (0.30 + 0.51 kg/ha)	17.14 ab	0.22 a	2.29 a	1.40 a
Anilofos (0.40 kg/ha)	15.70 b	0.22 a	2.26 a	1.40 a
Control	17.62 a	0.22 a	2.30 a	1.40 a
Time of azolla inoculation (d after herbicide application)				
On the day	0.61 c	0.06 c	2.32 a	1.42 a
3d day	16.33 b	0.22 b	2.35 a	1.44 a
6th day	23.91 a	0.24 a	2.41 a	1.47 a

^aIn a column within a factor, any two means followed by a common letter are not significantly different from each other by LSD (P = 0.05).

Irrespective of herbicide, inoculation of azolla 6 d after herbicide application had the highest FB.

The highest RGR (0.22 g/g per d) was in untreated control and in treatments

with anilofos. Azolla inoculation 6 d after herbicide application had the highest RGR.

Herbicides and times of inoculation had no effect on chlorophyll content. ■

Vesicular-arbuscular mycorrhizae (VAM) colonization in lowland rice roots and its effect on growth and yield

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VAM association is less frequent in submerged environments than in uplands. To study the colonization pattern of VAM and its effect on lowland rice growth and yield, we raised mycor-

rhizal seedlings in concrete pots (75 × 75 × 2.5 cm) filled with clay loam soil and pre-inoculated with the VAM fungus *Glomus fusciculatum* (3000 spores/0.25 m²). Dry nursery method was followed to facilitate VAM infection. Control seedlings were raised without VAM inoculation. Percent mycorrhizal colonization was recorded 21 d after.

Three sets of 20 seedlings each of mycorrhizal-infected plants and control were transplanted under flooded condition for observation of VAM 15, 30, and 45 d after transplanting (DT).

Crop response with and without NPK was tested in pots using inoculated and

uninoculated seedlings. The six treatments were laid out in a completely randomized design with four replications.

Inoculated seedlings recorded 16.2% VAM infection 21 d after inoculation. Infection persisted and further increased after transplanting. Infection was 20.8% at 15 DT, 28% at 30 DT, and 46% at 45 DT, indicating that flooding did not affect colonization. Control seedlings were also positive for infection at 21 DT because of native VAM. Infection was 8.6% at 30 DT and 14.2% at 45 DT.

Seedling growth and yield with and without NPK application were measured